

Illumination of Moral Values in “Sister Carrie”

Usmanova Ruzikhan Bozorovna

Teacher of Chirchik State, Pedagogical University

Abstract. *“Sister Carrie” is one of the first novels that openly describes a number of problems of unemployment, moral decay, and social life in America. The article talks about the importance of society and personal inclinations in the decline of human moral values.*

Key words: *biographical method, personality and society relations, personal tragedy.*

“Sister Carrie” is Theodore Dreiser's first novel. The origin of the idea of the work was based on the American life of the late 19th and early 20th centuries. When we get acquainted with the writer's autobiography, we can see that his childhood was spent in poverty, that he was forced to drop out of school due to family deficiencies, and that he often changed jobs due to low wages. The events of the work are based on the writer's own social life, the sad fate of the people around him, their inner world, spiritual experiences and sufferings. Based on this, it is appropriate to analyze the work based on the biographical method.

The first edition of the work was published in 1900. But the naturalistic ideas in the work are the cause of many discussions by critics. Naturalists were supporters of describing existing problems in society in accordance with their origin. “They believe that it is necessary to depict life as much as possible, without embellishing it, without directing it to any ideology or moral education goals. That is, naturalists believe that literature should not selectively describe the material of life, it should describe it as much as possible, there is no foreign subject or plot for literature.”¹ They pay attention to even the smallest details of the hero's life. As a result of the combined effect of artistic and social factors, the author placed two men, small salesmen, and a girl from a poor social background in the center of his first novel, and these characters appear before the reader against the background of the daily life of America, which is widely and carefully described. It has been.

Accordingly, before starting to describe Carrie's life in Chicago, it gives the addressee certain information about the character's phenotype, his life, family, social background, and the plot that is expected to happen in the development of events.

“If a girl who has seen eighteen springs leaves her father's house, she either falls into the hands of good people and her affairs go well, or she quickly succumbs to the influence of morals in the capital and becomes worse. There is no such thing as elegance.

A big city is a mine of cunning. The powerful forces in him attract and invite even the best-mannered sahibs to themselves with tricks. The shining of thousands of lights has no less effect than the beautiful caress of the eyes of the beloved, the spiritual decay of an innocent and simple soul is caused by the influences that first made a person dumb.”²

Carrie embodies the image of a simple country girl, a woman who rose from the lowest rung of society to the top, and in a certain sense, a lucky woman. Along the way, the writer integrates his views on

¹ Kuronov D., Mamajonov Z., Sheraliyeva M. Dictionary of Literary Studies.. – T.: “Akademnashr”, 2013. P. 203.

² Dreiser Theodor. Lucky Carrie. Translation by E. Nosirov. - T.: “Sharq”, 2007. P. 6.

the hero's experiences, unemployment in America, false relationships in the upper class of society, conspiracies, the sanctity of family and marriage into the system of images. Carrie is the epitome of thousands of young American women who come to the big city in search of work. A girl's biggest dream is to get used to city life, to take her place there, to live in good living conditions, to have her own job, house and a certain amount of money. But this is not an easy task.

The pure dreams of the girl began to be damaged in the scene of meeting Drue on the train. Her first job in the city was women's work in a shoe factory, the conditions created for them, a workplace full of the smell of leather and a low salary, the girl could not decide her future. The fate of many girls of that time was so sad. The influence of society, social life, and the environment was very great in their moral decline and collapse. The situations in the life of our hero, who entered the city with a world of dreams, are connected with the same objective reasons. In an effort to make her life easier, Carrie's life ended in tragedy, first with Drue and then with Hurstwood. The events of the play mainly revolve around the trio of Carrie, Drue and Hurstwood. Drue and Hurstwood are businessmen, and at the beginning of the play they are portrayed as relatively happy people who are lucky, successful in business, and successful in their personal lives.

If Drue's desire for an easy life, avoidance of responsibility in romantic relationships, distrust of family life alienated him from Carrie, similar indifference to moral values was the main factor in Hurstwood's decline. A huge capitalist city corrupts people's morals, makes them selfish, and causes the devaluing of feelings. Carrie's relationship with Drue is shown as a way to escape from poverty, while Hurstwood is shown as her true love and happiness. But all of these are not justifiable circumstances for that time or for the present time. All three heroes became victims of their dreams and desires. Among them, especially Hurstwood's life ended tragically. He deceived Kerry and his family in pursuit of his desires and passions.

Through the tragic fate of the hero, the writer showed how fragile the concept of luck and success is in human life, how selfish a person can be in the conditions of cruel competition, friendship based on interests, and the struggle for survival. In the events of the work, the author devotes a special place to expressing unemployment in New York, struggle for bread, and the poor way of life of people. The author mercilessly exposes the fact that thousands of Hurstwoods are forced to commit suicide. The fact that the improvement of the material condition of thousands of Kerrys is happening at the expense of their moral decline, the emergence of an unfillable void in their lives is revealed first through Minnie's dreams, and later through Carrie's dreams.

Minnie dreams that her sister has fallen first into an abandoned coal mine, and then into an abyss. This is a reference to Carrie's life after losing her sister. He left them in order not to be a burden to his poor sister and little one, and also to achieve his dreams more easily. Carrie later started having dreams about a rocking chair by the window. Through this, the writer emphasizes that Kerry's life is at a standstill, there is no way back or forward for her. By comparing the lives of Minnie and Carrie, it is clearly shown that money is not important for a person's happiness. As Minnie's life is going on, she is the mistress of a beloved family, but Carrie, having improved her financial situation, could not feel true happiness.

The writer expresses his conclusions in the following sentences:

“O. the confusion of human life! How superficially we understand many things! Here is the poor, simple and sensitive Carrie. He has a desire for all the nice things in life, but his forehead always hits a thick wall. Law: "Enjoy beautiful things if you want, but only achieve them in an honest way, do not approach them in any other way!" - would have said, of course.”³

The Creator does not mean the constitutional laws we are familiar with. An astute reader can quickly notice that he is reminding of the laws of Truth, the eternal and eternal rules of life.

The novel does not like the bourgeois government because it highlights the real lifestyle instead of showing the rich life in America. Dreiser conducts a deep psychological analysis of the lives of ordinary people. He includes some scenes from the life of himself and his relatives in the composition

³ Dreiser Theodor. *Lucky Carrie*. Translation by E. Nosirov. - T.: "Sharq", 2007. P. 510.

of the work. The first edition of the work was not put on sale, until 1904, readers were not happy to read it. Finally, 1904, Dreiser's first novel is published in London and becomes a great success.

References:

1. Kuronov D. Mamajonov Z., Sheraliyeva M. Dictionary of Literary Studies. - T.: "Akademnashr", 2013
2. Dreiser Theodor. Sister Carrie. Translation by E. Nosirov. - T.: "Sharq", 2007.